

IPBES Nexus Assessment

Chapter 5.5. Climate Change. Data Management Report. Case study – Box 5.5.6. Promoting sustainable healthy diets through plant-based public food procurement in Los Angeles County, USA.

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Description. This case study illustrates a bottom-up, governance Solution Option of **Sustainable healthy diets (C15)**. The case study in Box 5.5.6 *Promoting sustainable healthy diets through plant-based public food procurement in Los Angeles County*, was informed by a review of the literature, policy documents, city sustainability and government plans, and institutional initiatives promoting sustainable and healthy diets, and addressing nutrition and climate goals.

The case study in Box 5.5.6 is in the IPBES nexus assessment Chapter 5.5_Climate Change:

Options for delivering sustainable biodiversity-related approaches to climate change, adaptation and mitigation, including relevant aspects of the energy system. In “Thematic Assessment of the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services”. Harrison, P.A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T.L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn.

Introduction:

Los Angeles (LA) County, once the largest agriculture producer in the United States of America, has supported two bottom-up food justice initiatives: the “Good Food for All” movement and the LA Food Policy Council. The Good Food agenda engages farmers and communities in the development of local food systems, aiming to produce good food for all (healthy, sustainable, affordable, fair) while facilitating access through public procurement, farmers’ markets and community gardens. Despite these efforts, 30% of resident households (1 million people) were food insecure in 2023 and 50% of adults had pre- or diabetes. Climate change is impacting LA County through frequent and intense heat waves, droughts, wildfires, rainstorms and rising sea level, leading to land and biodiversity losses, food yield reductions and to higher food costs.

Policy Context

LA County has developed an innovative Sustainability Plan, focusing on community well-being, and an economy based on renewables, reduction of environmental impacts and climate adaptation (LA County, 2019). The Plan includes 12 cross-cutting goals. Goal 10 refers to a “Sustainable and just food system that enhances access to affordable, local, healthy foods”. The Plan Action 134 calls to ‘Promote plant-based menu options through nutrition and food procurement policies in food service settings in county facilities, hospitals, higher learning institutions, school districts, and jails, among others’. LA County enacted a *New Law in 2025* to

address health and environmental impacts associated with public food purchasing, by shifting into plant-based food procurement. The County committed to reduce food-based emissions by 25% from a 2025 baseline by 2035 (LA County Chief Sustainability Office, 2025).

The Good Food Purchasing Program

To bring equity and transparency to institutional purchasing, the LA Food Policy Council developed a values-based procurement policy: the Good Food Purchasing Program (GFPP), which includes standards on local economies, sustainability, workers' rights, animal welfare and nutrition. The City of LA and the LA Unified School District adopted the Good Food Purchasing Program in 2012, and the program was scaled-up at national level becoming the Center for Good Food Purchasing in 2015. The 2025 Board motion aligns the Good Food Purchasing Program principles and the new County food emissions reduction targets, making LA County the first in the USA to link institutional procurement standards directly to quantified climate goals.

Institutional Leadership

Several universities and hospital groups have shifted to serving healthy sustainable diets in order to promote health and reduce GHG emissions. The University of California Los Angeles (UCLA) increased its plant-based food procurement for students and patients. UCLA Health signed the "Cool Food Pledge" which is a commitment to a target of reducing GHG emissions associated with the food they serve by 25% by 2030, in line with the Paris Agreement long-term mitigation and adaptation goals. In 2025, UCLA Health announced a further expansion of its 'Healthy Climate Plate' initiative across its hospital network to align with County targets, emphasizing locally sourced produce and eliminating red meat entrées from its patient menus once weekly (UCLA Health Sustainability Update, 2025).

Social, Economic, and Environmental Benefits

Public food procurement plays a crucial role in facilitating access to healthy food for vulnerable groups such as schoolchildren, the elderly, and hospital patients, while creating local employment and supporting sustainable local agriculture. The new LA County motion highlights these co-benefits, and recognizes that '*equitable plant-based food access is integral to climate justice*,' aligning the initiative with the LA County's broader environmental and equity goals (LA County Chief Sustainability Office, 2025).

References

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UCLA Health. (2025). [Cool Food Pledge and Healthy Climate Plate Initiative](#).